

Kinematic analysis of experienced and inexperienced 0.5-point wheelchair rugby athletes

Oh Y-T^{a,*}, Mason B^a, Altman V^{a,b}, Briley S^a, Goosey-Tolfrey VL^a

^a The Peter Harrison Centre for Disability Sports, Loughborough University, Loughborough, UK

^b Sint Maartenskliniek, Nijmegen, Netherlands

*Corresponding author: Yim-Taek Oh; y.oh@lboro.ac.uk

Abstract The purpose of this study was to describe and compare the performance 3D kinematics between two wheelchair rugby players (WCR) with the same 0.5 sports classification but different levels of experience. Two spinal cord injured, 0.5-point WCR players (1 International (EXP) and 1 National (DEV)) volunteered for the study. Each player performed two sub-maximal speeds of 4, 6 km·h⁻¹ and a 15s all-out sprint on a dual-roller wheelchair ergometer in their WCR chairs. Forty-eight retroreflective markers were attached to each participant and the chair. 10 VICON cameras were used to track the marker trajectories. Joint-angles were calculated using MATLAB. For EXP the propulsion phase at 4 km·h⁻¹ was 51.4% and decreased to 28.3% during the sprint. Interestingly, the propulsion phase was similar for the DEV during both the 4 km·h⁻¹ and sprinting (38.2% and 39.6% respectively). EXP achieved a faster maximal speed than DEV (14.8 vs. 12.3 km·h⁻¹, while adopting a higher push rate during 15s all-out sprint (32 vs. 28 pushes). EXP showed better acceleration with peak speed being achieved after 4.9s after 11 pushes, while DEV took 10.7s to reach to the peak speed and almost twice as many pushes (n=20). At the first push of the sprint EXP displayed 11% greater shoulder extension (62.4°) than his other pushes (-31.8-46.7°), yet DEV showed similar range of flexion-extension angle at all time (-40.9-45.4°). EXP showed smaller adduction-abduction angle (11.5-41.1°) than DEV (25.8-50.0°). EXP pushed mostly at pronated position (-30.2--11.8°), whereas DEV used greater pro-supination (-15.4-14.9°). WCR experience clearly influences the propulsion and kinematics during wheelchair propulsion. Greater shoulder angles are displayed by EXP than DEV at the first push of sprint, yet smaller shoulder angles are evident once the wheelchair is accelerated. Experience clearly influences choice of push rates and the temporal timings between 4 km·h⁻¹ and sprinting, which appears yet to be learnt by the DEV player.

Keywords wheelchair rugby, kinematics, experience

Introduction

Effective biomechanics in wheelchair propulsion can increase the economy of wheelchair operation and lead an expeditious metabolic and cardiopulmonary demand (van der Woude, Bakker et al., 1998). In Wheelchair Rugby even though the experience of the athlete can be the major factor for effective wheelchair push, there has been no study examined its effect. The purpose of the present study is to describe and compare the performance 3D kinematics between two wheelchair rugby players (WCR) with the same 0.5 sports classification but different levels of experience.

Methods

Participants

Two spinal cord injured, 0.5-point Wheelchair Rugby players volunteered for the study. The expert athlete (EXP) was nominated as one of the best 0.5 class players world's largest sports event. He experienced several major events including Paralympic Games, World Championships and European Championships. The inexperienced athlete (DEV) is currently active at national level.

Process and variables

Each player performed two-submaximal speeds of 4, 6 $\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and a 15 s all-out sprint on a dual-roller wheelchair ergometer (WERG) in their WCR chairs. Forty-eight retroreflective markers were attached to each participant and the chair. 10 VICON cameras were used to track the marker trajectories. Wheelchair speed and power output were measured by WERG. Selected joint-angles (Shoulder flexion/extension, Shoulder adduction/abduction, Elbow flexion/extension, Pronation/supination) were calculated using MATLAB.

Figure 1. (a) Locations of forty-eight retroreflective markers attached to each participant and the chair and (b) its reconstructed image within VICON NEXUS software.

Results

For EXP the propulsion phase at 4 $\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ was 51.4% and decreased to 28.3% during the sprint. Interestingly, the propulsion phase was similar for the DEV during both the 4 $\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and sprinting (38.2% and 39.6% respectively). EXP achieved a faster maximal speed than DEV (14.8 vs. 12.3 $\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, while adopting a higher push rate during 15s all-out sprint (32 vs. 28 pushes). EXP showed better acceleration with peak speed being achieved after 4.9s after 11 pushes, while DEV took 10.7s to reach to the peak speed and almost twice as many pushes ($n=20$). At the first push of the sprint EXP displayed 11% greater shoulder extension (62.4°) than his other pushes (-31.8 - 46.7°), yet DEV showed similar range of flexion-extension angle at all time (-40.9 - 45.4°). EXP showed smaller adduction-abduction angle (11.5 - 41.1°) than DEV (25.8 - 50.0°). EXP pushed mostly at pronated position (-30.2 - -11.8°) at sprint, whereas DEV used greater pro-supination (-15.4 - 14.9°).

Figure 2. Result of the percentage propulsion phase of EXP and DEV at 4 km·h⁻¹ and Sprint.

	N of Push	Max speed (km·h ⁻¹)	NPMS*	TMS** (s)
EXP	32	14.8	11	4.9
DEV	28	12.3	20	10.7

Table 1. Result of sprint between EXP and DEV (*NPMS: Number of push to achieve Max-speed; **TMS: Time to achieve Max-speed).

Conclusion

WCR experience clearly influences the propulsion and kinematics during wheelchair propulsion. Greater shoulder angles are displayed by EXP than DEV at the first push of sprint, yet smaller shoulder angles are evident once the wheelchair is accelerated. Experience clearly influences choice of push rates and the temporal timings between 4 km·h⁻¹ and sprinting, which appears yet to be learnt by the DEV player.

Reference

Van der Woude LHV, Bakker WH, Elkhuisen JW, Veeger HEJ, Gwinn T. (1998) Propulsion technique and anaerobic work capacity in elite wheelchair athletes. *Am J Phys Med Rehabil* 77:222-234.